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International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/ijdr

Healthcare waste management for preparedness: shifting stakeholder salience in the disaster cycle

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1. Introduction

Despite the widespread recognition of the “do no harm” principle in disaster management and healthcare contexts, healthcare waste management (HCWM) remains underresearched [1,2]. Mismanagement of infectious or hazardous healthcare waste (HCW) not only threatens human health and environmental safety but also undermines preparedness by creating conditions conducive to the development of secondary disasters like infectious disease outbreaks and environmental crises [3,4]. This paper argues that to truly “do no harm” beyond the initial disaster response stage, HCWM should be integrated in the preparedness phase as an integral part of disaster management.

Operationally, disaster management is a cyclical process with multiple overlapping stages [5]. Consistent with the literature recognizing the disaster management cycle as a relevant framework for pre-disaster, during, and post-disaster activities [6,7] this study focuses on mitigation, preparedness, response and recovery phases.

Stakeholders involved in waste management (WM) are numerous and diverse, ranging from individuals to public and private organizations [8]. Stakeholder theory (ST) provides a framework for examining organizational accountability and stakeholder relationships in disaster management and public health contexts [9–11]. In disaster management and response, humanitarian organizations (HOs) often operate alongside public health authorities in HCW management (HCWM). Healthcare facilities and local communities also play a substantial role in supporting knowledge development, advocacy, and strengthening healthcare disaster response [12]. ST argues that organizations have obligations not only to shareholders, but to all entities affected by their activities [13]. This study uses the stakeholder salience framework [14] to facilitate mapping stakeholders’ roles as contextually dynamic.

Research on the consequences of HCW from disaster response has focused on decision support frameworks, the optimization of centralized and decentralized techniques for supply chain models, and environmentally optimal processing technologies [15,16]. Healthcare activities during disasters are context-specific and depend on various stakeholders with conflicting priorities and objectives [8]. Mitchell et al.’s [14] framework, while often represented as static and two-dimensional, is inherently dynamic and should be reassessed regularly to reflect shifting power, urgency, and legitimacy [17]. This paper examines the roles and influence of stakeholders in HCWM and their impact on preparedness, focusing on two questions.

- How can the effects of HCW, caused by disaster response, be minimised through preparedness?
- How does stakeholder salience evolve alongside the phases of the disaster cycle?

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2026.106267>

Received 20 February 2026; Received in revised form 22 May 2026; Accepted 17 June 2026

Available online 19 June 2026

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The paper is based on a comparative case study between Kenya and Vietnam, following a most-different systems design [18], to examine the roles and influence of formal and informal stakeholders in HCWM and their impact on system performance. The two countries differ considerably in disaster profile, governance structure, and health system capacity, but both have introduced national HCWM guidelines that mirror global standards [19,20]. Both face low awareness of the importance of HCWM, limited infrastructure, and constrained funding [21,22]. This combination makes them useful contexts for examining how expected standards are used and/or adapted in resource-constrained settings. Resource constraints and limited local capacity hinder the establishment of robust and resilient HCWM practices [23]. This study focuses on the planning and preparedness phase, which encompass multiple hazard types rather than being disaster specific.

2. Literature review

2.1. HCWM in resource-constrained contexts: the cases of Kenya and Vietnam

HCW streams are increasing in volume and complexity as access to healthcare expands globally [24]. HCW refers to “all waste generated within healthcare facilities, medical laboratories, and research centres”, as well as “waste produced from minor or scattered sources” such as home-based care, mobile clinics, or vaccination campaigns ([25]; p.3). The World Health Organization (WHO) classifies HCW into non-hazardous and hazardous waste [26]. Non-hazardous waste accounts for 75–90% of HCW and is comparable in composition to domestic waste, including paper, packaging, and food waste. Hazardous HCW may be toxic, infectious or radioactive, and requires specialized handling due to higher health risks, environmental impact, and management costs [27].

Typically, solid HCWM follows the process outlined in Fig. 1. Treatment will differ depending on the type of waste, with HCW commonly classified into seven categories: sharps, non-clinical, infectious, radioactive, chemical, pathological, and pharmaceutical waste [28]. Improper disposal of infectious waste (e.g., used needles, contaminated materials) can transmit diseases to healthcare workers, waste handlers, and the public [8,24,27]. Practices such as open burning or illegal dumping of HCW release toxic substances into air, soil, and water, leading to long-term environmental damage and health risks for surrounding communities [24,29].

HCWM is a critical yet underprioritized and underfunded component of public health systems, especially in resource-constrained contexts, such as Kenya and Vietnam [21,30,31]. However, the drivers, governance and technological responses through which these challenges manifest differ. Table 1 summarizes the similarities and differences between the two countries regarding HCWM.

Kenya's rapidly growing population requires access to healthcare due to frequent outbreaks of e.g. cholera and malaria [36]. The widespread use of single-use protective equipment has increased volumes of HCW, and access to incinerators is rare [36]. Despite policies, guidelines, and communication strategies for HCWM since 2007 [36], smaller healthcare facilities frequently lack access to safe treatment solutions, resulting in widespread open burning [36]. Hazardous and non-hazardous solid waste is disposed of through uncontrolled practices, often accumulating in public spaces [22,27]. Kenyan local government initiatives rely on stakeholder involvement, through consultative meetings, and awareness campaigns [22]. While knowledge of HCWM among hospital staff is strong [32], collective decision-making and information sharing is still limited [22]. A lack of clear indicators and comprehensive management approaches makes prioritization of HCWM performance difficult [34]. Low adherence to guidelines may also be due to hospital staff struggling to contextualize regulations within their local settings, making it challenging to achieve and enforce consistent standards [37].

Vietnam has a more centralized healthcare system with large hospitals located in major cities, serving patients from across multiple provinces [33]. This concentration creates local overload, leading to HCW generation rates exceeding WHO averages for comparable settings [21]. Solid HCW is managed by outsourcing to an authorized company, handling at centralized solid WM clusters and using on-site treatment systems located inside the medical facilities [21]. Unlike in Kenya, incineration is prohibited in large cities due to air

Fig. 1. HCWM process. Source: Authors' own work.

Table 1
Key similarities and differences in HCWM between Kenya and Vietnam.

Dimensions	Kenya	Vietnam	References
Policy and regulatory frameworks and enforcement	National HCWM regulations in place for almost 20 years Uneven enforcement and implementation gaps, especially in smaller facilities	Laws, decrees and circulars governing HCWM in place for several years Weak enforcement	Dang et al. [21] Khan et al. [27] Ministry of Health Kenya (2024) Muthoni et al. [32]
Governance structure	Emphasis on stakeholder consultation and awareness campaigns	Fragmented oversight across multiple authorities	Dang et al. [21] Ibrahim and Mbitaru (2023)
Drivers of HCW generation	Population growth Infectious disease outbreaks, increased use of single-use devices	Concentration of large hospitals in mega cities and high patient inflows	Ministry of Health Kenya (2024) Nguyen et al. [33]
Waste treatment infrastructures and dominant practices	Open burning Safer technologies mainly available in large facilities	Incineration and landfill in provinces and district healthcare facilities High-temperature steam-based autoclave integrated with waste cut-and-grind equipment in megacities	Dang et al. [21] Ministry of Health Kenya (2024)
Operational capacity and system gaps	Gap in staff training, prioritization and coordination Informal stakeholders	Reliance on ministerial guidance Limited internal healthcare facility HCWM rules Informal stakeholders	Githinji et al. [34] Marchesini [8] Nguyen [35]

pollution. Healthcare facilities therefore use non-burn technologies like high-temperature steam-based autoclave, integrated with waste cut-and-grind equipment [21], considered to emit fewer pollutants [38]. In Vietnam, law, decrees and circulars governing HCWM, particularly safe handling of infectious and hazardous waste and wastewater management, are well established [21]. However, HCWM governance is fragmented, involving multiple regulatory bodies including the Departments of: Health, Natural Resources and Environment, Science and Technology, and Water Resources Management [21], with healthcare facilities largely dependent on Ministry of Health regulations [35].

Despite these differences, both Kenya and Vietnam display similar outcomes in terms of weak HCWM enforcement [21,22,32], inconsistent implementation, inadequate training, and limited infrastructures [39]. When formal systems fail, informal stakeholders increasingly fill operational gaps, exposing themselves to significant health risks, while sustaining waste flows [8].

2.2. HCWM and disaster preparedness

Disasters impact life, property, livelihood, and industries, leading to lasting changes in societies and ecosystems [40]. Proactive strategies, such as mitigation and preparedness, focus on reducing risks, and are used to address long-term issues [41] such as poverty, inadequate governance, and weak infrastructure, which contribute to consequences of disasters [42]. Disaster risk is shaped by these underlying vulnerabilities and systemic conditions. [43]. A disaster can extend to a secondary disaster if the processes are poorly managed, which leads to future risks and potentially exploitation of those affected [1,44]. A secondary disaster exacerbates, extends, or complicates the impacts of the first disaster [45]. For example, natural disasters already present a severe public health effect due to direct injuries as well as trauma-based long-term symptoms but can also induce conditions for communicable diseases to thrive and develop into epidemics [46]. Limited and/or damaged water and sanitation infrastructure significantly increases disease risk, particularly when combined with displacement and overcrowding, and lack of adequate WM systems can pollute water sources, soil, and air [47,48]. The Ebola virus disease outbreak in West-Africa 2014-16 and the Covid-19 pandemic caused significant spikes in infectious waste, putting pressure on WM infrastructure [23]. Inadequate disposal practices, such as open burning and illegal dumping, contributed to further disease transmission through contaminated materials, affecting healthcare workers, waste handlers, and communities [39]. Due to overwhelmed WM systems, improper disposal methods caused increased infection risk for communities and environmental damage [24,29].

Funding for disaster response is often earmarked, time-limited, and focused on short-term impact, leaving limited scope for addressing systemic issues and associated infrastructures and expertise [49]. HCWM often falls on the receiving country, as donors avoid funding activities perceived as peripheral to life-saving interventions [4]. Many disaster response supply chains are temporary and established quickly, relying heavily on improvisation, swift trust, and short-term partnerships [50]. HCWM in disaster responses remains inconsistent and vulnerable to operational breakdowns, exacerbating risks [51]. HCWM is treated as a reactive activity, rather than a proactively managed system embedded in healthcare planning, leading to HCW mismanagement [29,52,53]. Effective HCWM requires a proactive preparedness model that brings together local knowledge, engaged stakeholders, and scientific processes [54]. Integrating HCW into healthcare planning, coordination structures and recovery strategies is widely recommended to strengthen system resilience [55]. Local knowledge is especially important, as communities often display notable adaptive capacity and resilience, providing valuable insights to preparedness strategies [56]. Engagement with disaster-prone and/or affected communities should be dynamic, which contributes to the context-specific adaptiveness of the humanitarian supply chain [54,57]. Local knowledge can further the shift from a linear to a more dynamic supply chain as (HC)WM includes deeply contextual elements. Many communities may already have functioning WM systems that combine informal and formal methods and stakeholders [58].

Kenya and Vietnam face recurring shocks such as typhoons and landslides (Vietnam) and epidemics (Kenya) that place severe

pressure on already constrained HCWM infrastructures [12,59]. During disaster relief, emergency medical teams (EMTs) are deployed to support healthcare and medical activities, especially in remote areas [59]. Similarly to other WM sectors [8], these teams rely on standard operating procedures (SOPs), derived from WHO guidance, to manage HCW efficiently and safely [12,59]. SOPs translate strategy into operations through written instructions on how a specific process can be performed to the same standards on every execution [60]. This standardization is part of a quality system, which encompasses for example the responsibilities of stakeholders across the process, and the resources available to complete it [61].

The interplay between the disaster cycle and the causes of secondary disasters is synthesised in Fig. 2. A secondary disaster, resulting from poorly managed disaster response processes, can further increase existing underlying vulnerabilities, potentially restarting the cycle. Mitigating underlying vulnerabilities is a vital step in reducing the consequences of disasters on communities, and enabling an effective response [54].

2.3. Stakeholder theory

ST defines stakeholders as those who can affect or are affected by an organization's activities [13], emphasizing an ethical and managerial responsibility toward multiple stakeholders [14]. Mitchell et al.'s [14] stakeholder salience model assign stakeholders three perceived attributes: power (ability to influence the organization), legitimacy (appropriateness of their claim), and urgency (criticality and time-sensitivity of their needs) [11,17]. Depending on the combination of these attributes, stakeholders are categorized into eight types (Fig. 3). Research has challenged the static nature of early stakeholder models, calling for more dynamic, context-sensitive, and relational perspectives [62,63].

Stakeholder dynamics emphasize that stakeholders are not fixed entities but continually involved in negotiations, conflicts and collaborations [64]. In disasters, the relative importance of stakeholders may rise or fade as the crisis unfolds [17], inherently raising urgency, often transforming stakeholder classifications [9]. Dormant stakeholders can become dangerous, discretionary stakeholders may become dependent and dominant stakeholders definitive when urgency spikes [9,10]. Moreover, Phillips [65] argues that legitimacy itself is conceptually complex, and distinguishes normative legitimacy, the moral right to be considered, and derivative legitimacy, which is a stakeholder's strategic influence. In this dynamic environment, stakeholder engagement becomes temporal and strategic.

Stakeholders with greater access to resources (funding, personnel and time) or control over resource allocations may exert more influence, affecting their salience [64]. Fassin [62] extends the traditional salience framework with a moral and representational hierarchy of stakeholders, distinguishing “real stakeholders” (those with legitimate claims and mutual power relations with the organization), “stakewatchers” (representatives of real stakeholders, such as pressure groups), and “stakekeepers” (external agents who impose responsibilities without the firm having reciprocal obligations). This is particularly visible in HCWM in disaster settings where non-governmental organizations act as “stakeseekers” [66], who amplify marginalized voices and reshape legitimacy and relationships [67].

Fig. 2. Risks linked with HCW mismanagement throughout the disaster management cycle. Source: Authors' own work.

Fig. 3. Stakeholder categories. Source: Mitchell et al. [14].

3. Methodology

3.1. Case study selection: Kenya and Vietnam

This study employs a qualitative comparative case study methodology, as it generates context-rich examples of stakeholder dynamics and management challenges, allowing researchers to uncover the reasons driving stakeholder behaviours and decisions, rather than imposing external interpretations that may misrepresent their true motivations [68]. Multiple case studies are often preferred for methodological rigor [69] and are particularly valuable when the boundaries between context and phenomenon are blurred, enabling an in-depth investigation of underlying mechanisms [70]. Recent research underlines the need for more comparative case studies in WM literature to highlight best practices, common challenges and synergies [16]. Comparative case studies should not be limited to a specific context, highlighting the need to seek out units of analysis that are appropriate to the task at hand [71].

Marmor et al. [72] demonstrate that comparing healthcare systems and policies allows international applicability. HCWM is characterised by highly standardized practices and strong reliance on international regulations that primarily emphasize HCWM technical compliance [27]. Comparing two national contexts serves as an analytical strategy to move beyond regulatory frameworks [21,30], and capacity shortages [73] at the system level, bringing attention to HCWM and dynamic stakeholder relations across disaster phases. Kenya and Vietnam have previously been examined together in agriculture, healthcare systems and business development research [74,75] as well as climate change preparedness [76].

The selection of Vietnam and Kenya as case study settings was made using a most-different systems design [18]. It involves purposefully selecting opposing cases that differ in characteristics [18]. If cases are different but produce a similar outcome, this can be explained by identifying their shared factors [71]. Kenya and Vietnam differ in geography (Southeast Asia and East Africa), political and administrative traditions, health-system organizations, disaster typologies and regulatory environments, but they are both lower-middle-income settings with recurrent disaster exposure, long-standing humanitarian presence, and established HCWM systems. Bloemraad [77] argues that we should decide what to compare, i.e. HCWM in disasters, and how. As this study focuses on the planning and preparedness phase, in which organizations rely on integrated SOPs designed to be adaptable across multiple hazard types, the findings emphasize cross-cutting governance challenges over hazard-specific differences. The most-different systems design allows the study to examine whether similar stakeholder salience dynamics and adaptive practices emerge across those two contrasting contexts. If comparable patterns are observed, findings are more plausibly attributable to underlying mechanisms such as phase-dependent urgency, redistribution of salience and local adaptive capacity rather than to a country-specific conditions.

3.2. Data collection

3.2.1. Non-participant observation

Contextual understanding is a fundamental condition for cross-country comparison [78]. Two three-week field visits were conducted in Vietnam (December 2024) and Kenya (June 2025). Non-participant observation was used to contextualize interview accounts regarding stakeholder roles in HCWM [79]. Observations focused on in-house waste handling, transportation systems, and disposal processes [79]. These immersive visits facilitated direct engagement with hard-to-reach stakeholders, enriching the depth and

diversity of the data. The field visits were not intended to test or validate theoretical claims but to provide contextual insights that informed interview design, case comparability, and interpretation of HCWM practices.

3.2.2. Interviews

27 semi-structured qualitative interviews, forming the study's primary dataset, were conducted with stakeholders from 12 organizations, including HOs, government agencies, private sector stakeholders, WM companies, and healthcare professionals (Table 1). Consistent with most cross-cultural studies, participants were recruited through convenience and snowballing sampling strategies [80], for their expertise on HCWM. HOs were included as relevant stakeholders in disaster management [59]. Interviews were conducted individually or in small groups, depending on institutional preferences and feasibility. The interviews ranged from 25 to 63 min in duration and continued until data saturation was reached, making additional interviews unlikely to yield new insights into stakeholder roles, coordination dynamics, and HCWM practices relevant to the research questions in both settings [81].

Based on the TENK 2019 principles of research with human participants in Finland, the ethical review conducted for the study did not require further examination. The study did not include direct interviews with patients or caregivers, despite their central position among underrecognized stakeholders affected by HCWM practices. This decision was made deliberately, given the heightened groups' vulnerability and the ethical challenges associated with that. Instead, the analysis draws on accounts from healthcare professionals, humanitarian stakeholders, and practitioners who regularly interact with patients and caregivers and mediate their needs within HCWM systems. While this approach does not substitute for direct engagement with this vulnerable population, it allows for critical examination of how patient and caregiver interests are represented or overlooked, within formal decision-making processes.

The interview guide was informed by the literature and focused on three key areas: HCWM's role in mitigating secondary disasters, stakeholder influence on HCWM and perceived risks associated with poor HCWM practices. All interviews were recorded, transcribed and, if required, translated into English. The data was analysed using NVivo which facilitated systematic coding and theme development.

3.2.3. Document analysis

EMTs from the authors' existing network of HOs, were invited to share their WM SOPs and guidance voluntarily. Only the ones specifically addressing HCWM (segregation rules, storage requirement, compliance, disposal and treatment methods, transportation) were included in the analysis. A total of 20 SOPs, summarized in Fig. 4, were analysed to identify key HCWM guidelines, specifically highlighting procedures in terms of segregation, collection, storage and disposal methods. Full details can be found in Appendix A.

These SOPs provide guidelines for EMTs to handle waste generated in their operations. The fundamental WM processes do not differ substantially from a hospital, but the emergency working conditions complicate HCWM further.

3.3. Data analysis

Following a most-different systems design [18], cases were analysed using identical analytical procedures to enable comparison at the level of abstract themes. The data was analysed using a hybrid deductive and inductive thematic coding [64,82]. All qualitative data was coded by a single researcher. Analytical rigor and consistency were ensured through an iterative and reflexive coding process,

Fig. 4. Summary of standard operating procedures' guidelines for HCWM. Source: Authors' own work.

rather than through inter-coder reliability measures. The coding involved three rounds of review, during which codes were refined, merged, or redefined to resolve redundancy and maintain conceptual coherence.

A detailed single codebook was maintained and updated throughout the analysis to document coding decisions, emerging patterns, and reflections on interpretation. This documentation supported transparency and traceability from first-order codes to higher-level themes. Joint coding enabled systematic comparison across materials, and source-specific analysis ensured that differences in perspective and function were preserved in this analysis.

The analysis began with a codebook of 17 terms derived from the literature related to HCW (“hazardous waste”, “non-hazardous waste”, “single use”), HCWM (“incineration”, “segregation”, “waste treatment”, “awareness raising”, “strategies”, “training”, “burning”, “bury”, “resources”, “standardization”), and stakeholders (“stakeholders involved in HCWM”, “turnover”, “regulatory frameworks”, “stakeholders involved in preparedness”). During the initial coding phase, additional codes were generated inductively through engagement with empirical material, resulting in 101 additional codes. This allowed us to build broader insights from specific observations, to identify recurring patterns and to use those patterns to generalize findings and generate theoretical contributions [83]. Throughout the coding process, redundancies and non-relevance in the coding were eliminated, e.g. the codes “aligning policies and practice” and “regulations but no compliance” were merged as both captured the disconnect between regulatory frameworks and operational realities. This resulted in a refined set of 109 codes (Appendix B). These first-order codes were then iteratively abstracted to yield 17 s-order themes (Table 2), which were consolidated into 4 third-order themes: (1) Waste type generators, (2) HCWM strategies, (3) Disaster management strategies, (4) WM as a norm (Table 3).

3.4. Research quality

High-quality qualitative research requires analysing and justifying the choices made to support the investigation of the phenomenon of interest [84]. Although data analysis was conducted by a single researcher, co-authors contributed to the rigor and trustworthiness of the study through their involvement in data collection and contextual grounding. Co-authors supported the development of interview guides, participant recruitment, and interpretation of contextual factors shaping HCWM practices. One co-author, based in Kenya, provided ongoing contextual feedback during the analytic process. Moreover, Vietnamese researchers and practitioners were

Table 2
Interviewees' characteristics. Source: Authors' own work.

Disaster type	Organization	Interviewee code	Position	Sector
Typhoon	ORG1	V1	Procurement officer	Humanitarian organization
Typhoon	ORG1	V2	Social work and disaster management committee officer	
Typhoon	ORG1	V3	Social work and disaster management committee officer	
Typhoon	ORG1	V4	Healthcare committee expert	
Typhoon	ORG1	V5	Health operations officer	
N/A	ORG2	PS6	Informal WM app founder	Private sector
Pandemic	ORG3	V7	Head of the environmental department	Humanitarian organization
Typhoon	ORG1 and ORG4	V8	Preparedness officer	
Landslides	ORG5	V9	Sustainability project officer	
N/A	ORG6	V10	Deputy General Director	
N/A	ORG6	V11	Deputy director of bureau of employer activity	
Typhoon	ORG7	V12	Disaster reduction program manager	Humanitarian organization
Landslides				
Typhoon	ORG8	V13	Climate Change Technical Advisor	Healthcare facility
Landslides				
Typhoon	ORG9	V14	Radiation and Safety Officer	
Landslides Epidemic				
Typhoon	ORG9	V15	Dean of a Medicine and Public Health Institute	
Landslides Epidemic				
Epidemic	ORG10	K16	Nurse, holder of the facility	Humanitarian organization
Pandemic				
Epidemic	ORG10	K17	Public Health Officer	
Pandemic				
Epidemic	ORG10	K18	Public Health Officer	
Pandemic				
Pandemic	ORG10	K19	Machine operator	
Pandemic	ORG10	K20	Incinerator operator	
Pandemic	ORG10	K21	Machine operator (incinerator + shredder)	
Pandemic	ORG11	K22	Incinerator operator	
Epidemic	ORG11	K23	Medical lab officer	
Pandemic				
Epidemic	ORG11	K24	Infection, prevention and control officer	
Pandemic				
Epidemic	ORG11	K25	Hospital housekeeper	
Pandemic				
Pandemic	ORG12	K26	Pest and control officer	
Pandemic	ORG12	K27	Trainee in pest and control	

Table 3
Second-order codes with representative quotes. Source: Authors' own work.

Disaster cycle	Third-order codes	Second-order codes	Representative quotes	
Response	Waste type generators	WM generators	"when the disaster happens in some particular province, there's an absence of the people from the headquarter, so the staff in the province, they need to directly deal with those donations. And most of the time, they cannot manage. And then, it creates lots of problems at the end, because they cannot distribute those items to the community, and then they need to find a solution to handle them, maybe to pay extra money to send it somewhere. [...] it's a waste. If they don't know how to handle, actually it creates a problem." (V8)	
		Types of waste	"For the major sources of medical waste, maybe the giving sets, the dressing, the sharps. [...] And also drugs and drug containers. The ones that come from pharmacy packs. And then the ones with bottles for reconstitution. So, that also makes a bigger bunch of big waste." (K16)	
		WM stakeholders	"mostly waste management we have to involve the whole institution because waste management is all people in the institution because the waste are infectious" (K14)	
Recovery	HCWM requires coordination and collaboration	Relations between stakeholders	"In Vietnam, the informal sector, they go along the household, along the residential quarter, along the road to buy the recyclables. They sell to the second consolidator or the facilitator recycling company." (V9)	
		Challenges to HCWM	"we have various health facilities around within Kisumu. They [smaller hospitals] request us at times to incinerate the waste for them. So the assembly was contracted to be collecting the waste from outside and bring them to buy hazardous" (K17)	
Mitigation	HCWM strategies	HCWM process	"Medical waste within this hospital is handled per department, on a departmental basis. There are departments where we use coded bins, but there are departments where we don't need actually all the coded bins. So each department generates its own waste, and then it has the hygiene staff whose responsibilities are to collect the waste." (K21)	
		Necessary to an efficient HCWM	"There is a tracking system. The statistics are recorded by the system and sent directly to the Department of Natural Resources and Environment. The regulation of implementing the tracking systems depends on the company's functions and discharge flow rate. [...] By the end of the year, the company must report the wastewater analysis." (V8)	
		Opportunities linked with HCWM	"the waste pickers that I know in Nairobi, they are charging, I think, about three dollars a month for a weekly pickup of sorted waste. So, you're not just earning from the recycled materials, you're also earning from the houses that are having their materials picked up." (PS6)	
		WM participates to community protection	"Now, to manage the waste, or to reduce our carbon footprint, now we try to change the morality of the response. We provide the care transfer to the affected community members." (V13)	
		Consequences of HCW mismanagement	"We are prone to risk. We are dealing with the death directly. So at times we inhale this toxic smoke, that can affect us. Sometimes due to poor segregation from sources, you may find a sharp put in a wrong line above, mistakenly. So while handling waste, that can break you." (K17)	
		Waste reduction strategies	"Ideally, in the lab, we don't use the disposable ones. We buy the linen ones. You can use it for as long as you can. But when they're cleaned, then they're left." (K21)	
		WM as a norm	Regulatory challenges	"The challenging is first from the policy, that some policy is not very clear and it's not easy to comply. This means the enforcement is not easy." (V11)
			Stakeholders building agreements and legislations	"Normally, when this disaster happens, we, [...] sign agreement contract with the supplier that we require them to implement the green practice to [...] minimize the waste during, the supply chain, their supply chain." (V13)
			Disaster management strategies	"So, [HO] acting on the central ... on the central calls ... on the call centre at the county, they were collecting patients from all over and then bringing to the hospital where we had a tent. And the [HO] guys also was there." (K16)
		Preparedness	Disaster management strategies	Healthcare stakeholders during disasters
Humanitarian action does not prioritize sustainability Preparedness strategies	"Green affects preparedness by supporting environmental situations so that those kinds of disasters will not happen in the future, and it can reduce the costs of emergency relief." (V2)			
Leveraging capacities	"I always organize workshops for them. And I train them how they're supposed to be handling things within the hospital and the waste. Workshop training. I always organize for them workshop training." (K23)			

informally consulted before and after the data collection process to ensure that the data accurately represented field realities.

Emerging themes and interpretations were discussed among the research team, enabling reflexive consideration of alternative readings and context-specific meanings. Cacace et al. [85] propose six criteria to assess the quality of cross-country comparisons, which are applied to this study in Table 4.

Table 4
Research quality. Source: adapted from Cacace et al. [85].

Quality criterion	Definition	Applied to the study
Appropriate use of theory	Should be grounded in theory that structures what is compared and why. It informs the research design, guides the selection of cases and supports the analysis and interpretation of data	The stakeholder salience framework guided the identification of relevant stakeholders involved in HCWM Shaped the initial codebook and supported the interpretation of how stakeholder roles and influence shift across disaster contexts
Explicit selection of comparator countries	The selection of countries should be explicit, analytically justified and aligned with the research aim. Cases should be chosen for their relevance to addressing the research questions and the purpose of comparison	Kenya and Vietnam were deliberately selected due to substantial differences in drivers, governance and technological responses, while being similarly exposed to disaster risks and persistent HCWM challenges. This makes them suitable for a most-different systems design aimed at identifying analytically comparable patterns across divergent contexts rather than surface similarities
Rigor of the comparative design	Should be systematic and coherent with the aim of the study	Comparative case study design Application of identical coding procedures and thematic abstraction across both cases enables a systematic cross-case analysis
Attention to the complexity of cross-national comparison	Must address the complexity of comparing different contexts by providing sufficient contextual details Rich descriptions are necessary to avoid oversimplifying conclusions and support meaningful interpretation of similarities and differences	A rich description of both contexts is provided Collaborators living and working in each of the contexts have validated the descriptions Comparison is limited to HCWM while acknowledging differences in healthcare systems, disaster profiles etc
Rigour of the research method	Internal consistency between research questions, design and methods as well as transparency in data collection and analysis	Data collection and analysis processes are described and justified in detail Research design and methods have been carefully tailored to answer the research questions.
Contribution to knowledge	Cross-country comparisons should make a distinct contribution to theoretical advancement and/or policy learning by generating insights that extend beyond single-case findings	Demonstrates the dynamic nature of stakeholder salience across disaster phases Offers policy insights by highlighting the critical role of underrecognized stakeholders in HCWM and by informing disaster preparedness and WM strategies in diverse settings.

4. Results

Interviews demonstrated how different stakeholders engaged in HCWM across the disaster cycle. The findings reveal a distinction between how HCWM is planned during preparedness and mitigation and how it is executed during disaster responses. The perspectives of patients and caregivers presented in this section are not drawn from direct interviews with these groups, but are reconstructed through the accounts of healthcare professionals, humanitarian stakeholders, and practitioners who interact with them during HCWM operations. The analysis therefore reflects how underrecognized stakeholders are perceived, prioritized, or overlooked within formal decision-making processes, rather than how they experience HCWM practices themselves.

4.1. Mitigation

Interviewees describe HCWM as a key mitigation mechanisms aimed at reducing health and environmental risks during and after crises. National authorities in Kenya have sought to institutionalise WM through policies. The analysed SOPs similarly emphasized responsible sourcing and material selection as mitigation strategies to reduce downstream HCWM pressures, highlighting how procurement and supply decisions shape WM during disaster response. Vietnamese HOs (ORG1, ORG4) reported promoting cash-based assistance over in-kind donations to reduce inappropriate or surplus goods, thereby limiting waste volumes during crises.

“[Product] quality sets the foundation for the sourcing process [...] sustainability supports quality” (K16)

SOPs prescribe detailed requirements for WM. Guidelines derived from WHO recommendations assume a linear and standardized HCWM process in which all stakeholders are clearly defined and coordinated. Interviewees described continuous training aimed at reinforcing HCWM practices, following international HCWM practices.

“I always organize for them workshop training. And at times with the Public Health, they always invite me for their workshop also. When they are training and I get some other techniques, I keep on going in management of Western infection control.” (K25)

Kenyan respondents emphasized that standardized HCWM practices are intended to mitigate risks associated with staff turnover and recurrent epidemics. Healthcare workers segregate waste, hospital administrators coordinate compliance and logistics, holding decision-making power, supported by funds from the public health department for WM, cleaners secure bins, liners and trolleys, machine operators incinerate the waste, procurement officers collaborate with frontline staff to ensure appropriate equipment was available, and the national government ensures uniformity across counties. Employees of a Kenyan hospital (K16, K17, K18, K25, K26) explained that standardized HCWM practices are incorporated into staff induction, reinforced through both continuous and periodical

training, and monitored by county public health departments.

“Normally, this follows the government regulations. All staff must be trained. The training centre belongs to the government. The centre is licensed by the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Labour, Invalids, and Social Affairs. They are the government bodies responsible for this kind of training. The staff training is not only for this factory, but other factories will join online training.” (K17)

While compliance is uneven, standardized practices are viewed as essential for maintaining operational continuity. Limited exposure to infectious waste during outbreaks, investment in incinerators with scrubbers was highlighted as a way to comply with Kenyan HCWM protocols, while reducing emissions.

“Now we are having the new one incinerator. Maybe next week they can open it. We have the new one there. The brand new one. [...] Scrubber they have. They are still in everything.” (K26)

In Vietnam, mitigation efforts relied on facility-level implementation, reflecting a lower degree of urgency from local municipalities and government. Public hospitals reported developing internal HCWM plans, certification and procurement standards, primarily through government-issued circulars, alongside the designation of health, safety and environment units to oversee compliance. These measures aimed to embed standardized practices more firmly within healthcare facilities routines. Health, safety, and environment units within hospitals oversee compliance with standardized workflows, supported by mandatory training and certification.

“The classification method has already been guided by circulars. There will be waste that can be recycled, such as scrap paper, cardboard, plastic, saltwater bottles, glass, and metals such as milk cans and soft drink cans, bottle of mineral water.” (V14)

Large hospitals further mitigate risks by outsourcing hazardous waste treatment to licensed companies and, infrastructure permitting, processed recyclables. According to the head of ORG3's environmental department (V7), standards continuity was guaranteed by government control, and that WM transporters and WM companies need to be nationally certified in Vietnam. Unlike Kenya, Vietnamese WM companies play a central role in hazardous waste treatment, with incineration closely monitored by national authorities.

“Every [waste management] license like this is signed by the Minister of the Environment. It lasts 7 years. [...] So, every 7 years, they [waste management companies] apply for an upgrade for capacity.” (V7)

Beyond healthcare facilities, mitigation was more prominently supported by national-level initiatives and HOs, particularly through community-based WM pilots. Several organizations piloted projects designed to strengthen local waste systems. For example, ORG5 implemented initiatives to convert organic waste into fertilizer, training village heads to oversee segregation practices and strengthen compliance at community level.

4.2. Preparedness

In both countries, preparedness for HCWM was formally anchored within healthcare facilities, where standardized frameworks define roles, responsibilities, and resource needs in anticipation of sudden waste surges. Kenyan healthcare facilities were described as the core preparedness units. Facility managers held decision-making power, supported by public health department funding for WM. Interviewees strongly emphasized the importance of personal protective equipment to protect themselves from injuries and contamination. Procurement officers emerged as key intermediaries, collaborating with frontline staff to ensure the availability of essential equipment (liners, bins, trolleys). To nurses and public health officers procurement was central to preparedness as material shortages directly constrained compliance with HCWM standards.

Despite strong formal commitment to standardized HCWM frameworks, Kenyan interviewees consistently highlighted capacity constraints that undermined preparedness. Staff shortages and high turnover diminished continuity, requiring constant retraining and weakening enforcement mechanisms. ORG11 relied on a single incinerator operator, and one medical lab officer (K23) acknowledged no contingency measures in the operator's (K22) absence.

“We have to just wait for him to come back. [...] Fortunately, he's never gone for long. We are praying for him not to get sick.” (K23)

Public health officers reported shortages in implementation resources, which weakened the healthcare workers' ability to follow, and at times break HCWM guidelines. Sustainability considerations were acknowledged, but remained secondary due to immediate budgetary, safety and infrastructure constraints.

“Our other wish is if we could have just a disposal bucket just for the plastics, but we're incapacitated as a facility because of procurement issues.” (K17)

In Vietnam, HOs played a more visible role in preparedness, particularly through disaster-risk reduction campaigns. HOs (ORG4, ORG7, ORG8) noted that explicit links between these preparedness activities and HCWM were limited.

“For the waste management in the humanitarian context, [...], I think it's essential [...], because it ensures the hygiene and the community health.” (V12).

A humanitarian respondent (V12) argued that WM should not be treated as a disaster-specific concern, but rather approached as a

holistic and flexible capacity, embedded in communities and activated by HOs when a disaster strikes. Framed this way, WM can meaningfully contribute to preparedness and capacity building, particularly in resource-constrained contexts prone to recurring disasters.

“waste management shouldn't focus on a typical disaster, like for waste management, for a landslide, or waste management for a typhoon. [...] it should be a holistic waste management for disaster so whenever the flood, or typhoon, or landslide happens, we still have that system existing in the community, so we can activate that.” (V12)

Nonetheless, responsibility for HCWM in Vietnam remained concentrated within healthcare facilities. Vietnamese public hospitals reported developing internal HCW treatment plan, certification and procurement standards as part of preparedness efforts, but ultimately contracted licensed WM companies to handle HCWM operations. This outsourcing was viewed as a way to secure preparedness capacity in the absence of internal infrastructure expertise.

“Letting a hospital handle its own medical waste is very difficult, because getting an environmental permit is very difficult, getting a hazardous waste treatment permit is even more difficult. The fine is also very high, so hospitals prioritize hiring an outside unit, instead of investing in a technology that costs money to operate and then costs money to pay fines” (V15)

In Kenya, patients were not recognized as HCWM stakeholders, leaving them unprepared, despite their proximity to waste generation and exposure risks. This reveals a gap between standardized preparedness models and the realities of HCWM during disasters.

“The patients themselves, because they are not being trained. [...] they mix those polyethylene, even though they are labelled, but you find a patient, maybe she was admitted today, or she was admitted now, she doesn't know where to dump those wastes.” (K25)

4.3. Response

During disaster response, HCWM operated through dynamic and expanded networks that extended beyond formally mandated stakeholders. While ministries, healthcare facilities, and licensed waste operators retained regulatory legitimacy, interviewees consistently noted that many of these stakeholders lacked the practical power to fully control HCWM processes during periods of acute strain. As waste volumes surged and time pressures intensified, influence over HCWM shifted toward stakeholders with operational proximity and situational urgency.

In Kenya, healthcare facilities rapidly adapted their HCWM systems during the Covid-19 response. Facilities doubled waste treatment capacity by extending incinerator operating hours and recruiting additional waste-handling staff.

“during such crisis, we also upscale the collection. [...]. If maybe they were doing it twice in a day, now they would have to do it three times in a day too, in order to make up for this high level of waste production. And then also incineration. We have only one incineration point and you see it's serving other areas. So, we'll be giving priority to the Covid waste always, so that they don't stay there for long. We advise when they come from the ward, let us know which department is producing this and then they go straight to the incinerator.” (K15)

National authorities coordinated information flows and disaster planning, while HOs contributed primarily to non-medical operations such as patient triage and transportation. The PPE used by HOs was integrated into healthcare facilities' waste streams and treated within the facilities, reinforcing the centrality of hospitals as operational hubs for HCWM during response.

“Everything that was generated within the hospital was supposed to be disposed, just within the hospital. We were not supposed to send them outside.” (V1)

During the Yagi typhoon, Vietnamese HOs focused their HCWM-related response efforts on risk awareness campaigns in remote areas, seeking support from donors. To ensure the effectiveness of these campaigns, HOs strategically engaged village heads, whose social authority enabled them to translate HCWM urgency into locally accepted practices. Several organizations (ORG5, ORG8) also invested in youth engagement, through school-based campaigns aimed at promoting safe, hygienic living environment, and non-hazardous waste reduction, recognizing young people as influential intermediaries within households.

“After the Yagi typhoon, [...] local community and government authorities start, they usually have the plan, to work together to clear to ensure the hygienic environment, living environment around them” (V12)

Informal stakeholders played a significant yet contested role during the Vietnamese response phase. Informal waste pickers retrieved non-hazardous material, primarily plastics, from collection areas, and sold them to recycling facilities, thereby influencing waste flows and relieving pressure on formal systems. However, government efforts to restrict informal waste activities significantly reduced their institutional legitimacy. Interviewees noted that the unorganized nature of informal waste picking made these stakeholders particularly vulnerable to exclusion.

Patients and caregivers also emerged as influential response-phase stakeholders. Their behaviour, shaped by urgency and proximity to waste generation, affected both the volume and composition of HCW. Participation in segregation-at-source, identified in SOPs as critical HCWM strategy, often depended on patients' and caregivers' awareness and compliance, underscoring how response effectiveness relief on stakeholders who remained outside formal HCWM structures.

“Usually on admission, [...], the ones who are admitted may be too sick to be told about waste management. So, we normally talk to the caretakers. So, you tell them where to segregate waste [...] when you use diapers, please dispose them in such a place. When you use the bottles, please dispose them in such a place. [...] So even the ones who come on a regular basis, they're told this is what you're supposed to do, and the importance of the segregation.” (K16)

4.4. Recovery

In Kenya, recovery efforts were driven by healthcare facilities and focused on capacity building. K26 highlighted that some facilities invested in infrastructure renovations to reduce emissions and health risks:

“Now we are having the new one incinerator. Maybe next week they can open it. We have the new one there. The brand new one. [...] Scrubber they have. They are still in everything.” (K26)

Respondents from healthcare facilities (K20, K21, K22) explained that smaller facilities often lack sufficient incineration capacity to manage the volumes of waste generated, particularly in the aftermath of a disaster. As part of the recovery efforts, this excess waste is typically transferred to larger provincial hospitals for processing. However, K21 mentioned that contractors would sometimes deliver additional hazardous waste beyond what had been agreed upon, placing unanticipated pressure on receiving facilities and increasing the risks of waste mismanagement.

In Vietnam, ORG1's Health operations officer (V5) mentioned that healthcare facilities support the creation of training modules and the use of certifications on HCWM. They mentioned ensuring HCW standards by assigning a health, safety and environment unit. However, findings showed that recovery was more prominently supported by national government initiatives and HOs, who piloted community-based WM programs. ORG5's project promoted converting organic waste into fertilizer, with village heads trained and engaged to ensure compliance with segregation practices.

“After the disaster, usually the Heads of villages, they will ensure that the waste clearing happens. and then they will report back to the People's Committee at the common level, so if they have their level reporting and monitoring.” (V13)

Additionally, ORG5 and ORG8 have been investing in local communities and especially the youth, through awareness raising campaigns to promote a safe and hygienic living environment thanks to non-hazardous waste reduction best practices.

“After the Yagi typhoon, [...] local community and government authorities start, they usually have the plan, to work together to clear to ensure the hygienic environment, living environment around them” (V12)

Finally, in Vietnam, the informal sector was strongly involved in recovery activities, playing the role of recyclable collectors for private WM companies. This allowed to create a parallel waste market, which not only creates economic opportunities for a part of the informal sector, but also allow to control where the waste ends up.

Fig. 5. Stakeholders' saliences change during the disaster management cycle. Source: Authors' own work.

5. Discussion

This study draws on stakeholder salience to examine how power, legitimacy and urgency shape HCWM for disaster preparedness, and to show why reactive, compliance-oriented approaches repeatedly underperform in resource-constrained settings. Our findings argue for designing HCWM as a preparedness capability governed across phases, rather than as a residual task during response and recovery [24–27]. In Kenya and Vietnam, surges in hazardous waste, infrastructure gaps and uneven enforcement produced operational bottlenecks and risk spillovers, consistent with evidence that HCW mismanagement can lead to secondary disasters [1,29,51].

5.1. Disasters reconfigure stakeholders' roles and influence: salience is relational and temporal

This research contributes to stakeholder salience by specifying how and why salience reconfigure across the disaster cycle in HCWM and by clarifying a distinct channel of power. While often discussed in terms of resource control, stakeholder salience emphasizes that power frequently derives from social position, i.e. the authority, institutional mandate or formal role a stakeholder holds within a system, rather than the material resources they possess [86]. The findings nuance this theoretical understanding by showing that practical HCWM frameworks often treat stakeholders' power and capacities as static. This helps explain why operational influence may increase for stakeholders with limited resources (heads of villages, patients, etc.) and decrease for stakeholders assumed to be powerful in standardized frameworks (HOs) when urgency escalates and SOPs meet capacity constraints [17,62,64].

Fig. 5 illustrates the dynamic stakeholder reconfiguration, empirically demonstrating Alpaslan et al.'s [9] argument that increased urgency transforms stakeholder roles, and salience reshapes hierarchies. Empirically, the data shows that salience shifts depend on disaster phases among Mitchell et al.'s [14] categories: dependent to definitive (Kenyan health workers during response), dependent to demanding (Vietnamese communities as urgency rose) and dominant/definitive to dependent (HOs). These patterns confirm that salience is relational and temporal [62,64,87] and is shaped by crisis dynamics and institutional responsiveness [10,14,17]. In both Kenya and Vietnam, recurring disasters consistently reconfigure stakeholder roles and influence, compressing coordination timelines and redistributing responsibilities in ways that SOPs can only partially cover. The contextual variation thus helps explain differences in how HCWM is prioritized and adjusted in practice and why stakeholder salience in HCWM is better understood as relational and temporal rather than fixed.

The analysis underscored four mechanisms that explain salience shifts and HCWM under disasters (Fig. 6). First, rapid increases in hazardous waste leverage urgency and reorder stakeholder hierarchies. These surges give definitive status to stakeholders that are the closest to the point of risks (healthcare workers), whose decisions immediately affect continuity of care and exposure. Healthcare workers in Kenya went from a compliance-oriented role in the mitigation, preparedness and recovery phases (dependent) to central stakeholders (definitive) in the response phase, when their urgency surged due to rapidly increasing waste volumes.

Second, the rigid application of national and WHO standards where infrastructure, skills and oversight are limited, often produces implementation gaps, circumvention, and unintended shifts in responsibility. These gaps weakened assumed roles of formally designated stakeholders and redirected practical salience away from them. Although shared rules and standardization, are essential for coordinated action [88], and for ensuring safe, predictable and efficient HCWM [25,26,89], the findings show that standardization operates along two dimensions: (1) a policy discourse embedded in national regulations and WHO guidelines; and (2) an operational approach of HCW segregation, transportation, storage, and disposal. Extending Caniato et al.'s [90] insights to the healthcare sector, the results indicate that government's normative legitimacy enabled them to impose requirements that are misaligned with existing infrastructural and institutional capacities [65]. As a result, rigid frameworks may constrain other stakeholders' ability to adapt, innovate, and go beyond regulations, thereby weakening collective contribution to HCWM during HCW surges. These

Fig. 6. Mechanisms explaining stakeholder salience shifts in HCWM during disasters. Source: Authors' own work.

governance-driven constraints limited the ability of certain formally mandated stakeholders (such as healthcare workers and WM companies) to exercise the power and urgency they are assumed to have in standardized HCWM models, showing that their salience is weaker in practice, undermining the overall quality of HCWM.

Third, governments and WM companies may retain normative legitimacy [65] yet lack operational reach during HCW surges. Simultaneously, when formal systems are overwhelmed, informal workers and community networks expand activity (recovery of recyclables, waste collection support, etc.), relieving pressure on saturated WM systems. However, they lack protection or recognition from governments. These findings align with Phillips' [65] critique of narrow definitions of stakeholder legitimacy, which overlook stakeholders who hold no formal recognition, yet exert meaningful influence. The exclusion of stakeholders who lacked formal legitimacy from HCWM policy frameworks contributed to coordination gaps and inefficiencies that, as Mitchell et al. [14] argue, can undermine the claims of formally legitimate stakeholders. Vietnamese waste pickers expanded their contributions during crises by recovering recyclables and reducing pressure on formal systems. Yet, their legitimacy was undermined by regulatory restrictions, revealing the undervalued role of informal stakeholders in governmental WM strategies. Consistent with research on solid WM in Kenya [22] and studies emphasizing local stakeholders as key contributors to operational implementation [56], their marginal role in planning represents a missed opportunity for participatory disaster preparedness. This calls for a shift away from top-down models to adaptive, locally informed approaches that reflect the realities of populations and enhance community ownership of preparedness [56, 91].

Finally, institutional mandate and community standing allow stakeholders with limited material resources such as heads of villages to translate national/WHO guidance into applicable local rules, share compliance routines, and coordinate low-tech contingencies. HOs leveraged heads of villages to promote behavioural change during mitigation. These leaders, holding legitimacy from their social position and community recognition, enabled HOs to enforce segregation and sustain WM flows in last-mile settings during disaster response and recovery where formal capacity is limited. This demonstrates that stakeholder salience can arise not only from formal authority, but also from the urgency and legitimacy of claims made by stakeholders who often remain marginalized [92]. Effective preparedness therefore requires integrating scientific and local knowledge systems and training community stakeholders as core partners in preparedness, recognizing local stakeholders as key contributors to mitigation assessment and implementation [56,57].

5.2. The effects of stakeholder salience changes on WM capacities

Disasters disrupt established governance arrangements, forcing stakeholders to rely on improvised responses that deviate from formal protocols [6]. In WM research, this disruption has often led to calls for more research on the organizational, legal and financial framework of disaster WM [93], while overlooking the role of stakeholder dynamic in shaping WM outcomes. Focus remains on institutional coordination among formal stakeholders, primarily national governments and local municipalities [94]. Similarly, in disaster relief literature, HOs typically hold a prominent role [95]. The study's data nuance these conclusions by underlining that the role of HOs in HCWM is, in practice, largely symbolic and more limited than the literature suggests. During the mitigation phase, HOs primarily acted as awareness facilitators, raising public and institutional consciousness about environmental and health risks,

Fig. 7. HCWM integrated in the disaster management cycle. Source: Authors' own work.

positioning them as stakewatchers, who act to protect community interests [62], rather than as central to HCWM mitigation operations.

Consequently, as salience shifts along the disaster management cycle, resources are redirected toward high-salience stakeholders (national government, healthcare workers, waste management officers and healthcare facility managers). Situated at the centre of the waste surge, these stakeholders are able to recognize HCWM as a way to mitigate secondary disasters caused by infection transmission and injuries, and therefore as a risk mitigation tool rather than downstream strategy. Fig. 7 captures this dynamic by summarizing the definitive stakeholders in HCWM throughout the disaster management cycle. While the salience of stakeholders shifts across the phases and the definitive stakeholders change, the figure illustrates that coordinated engagement between national government, municipalities, healthcare providers, WM companies and HOs can reduce the risks for local communities. By addressing underlying vulnerabilities, these stakeholders can strengthen resilience in the community and reduce the likelihood of secondary crises. More streamlined HCWM, in disasters and otherwise, is accomplished by the healthcare and WM sectors, hence their inclusion in the relief process is compatible with preparedness and mitigation activities. Because of the changing stakeholder salience, a collaborative approach encompassing the definitive stakeholders throughout the cycle is necessary to fully realise the opportunities of HCWM and lessen secondary disaster risk. The figure highlights that preparedness-oriented HCWM depends on the combined action of these stakeholders, who are crucial to the integration of HCWM in disaster management to achieve a more resilient post-disaster community.

The findings in Vietnam and Kenya further demonstrate that the partial formalization of community roles is doable. HCWM literature has increasingly acknowledged the role of informal WM stakeholders in resource-constrained settings [96,97], and disaster management research has also started to recognize the importance of community engagement in preparedness ([56]). However, neither stream has adequately researched what happens when the operational responsibility defaults to stakeholders who are not formally recognized during WM disruption.

5.3. HCWM as a preparedness strategy: standardization with adaptive capacity

The findings highlight the potential to reposition HCWM from a post-disaster activity to an important element across all phases of the disaster cycle [29]. Proactive HCWM planning, embedded into preparedness frameworks, not only improves immediate disaster response, but also has the potential to mitigate secondary health disasters, reduce environmental degradation, and enhance system resilience. Specifically, our results underline that HCWM standardization should be coupled with the flexibility of adaptive practices [54,57]. In contexts where healthcare workers struggle to contextualize regulations within their local settings, further impairing HCWM enforcement [37], this study emphasizes the role of local capacity as contextually embedded adaptations that may help address operational gaps arising in disaster-affected settings. Local knowledge is understood as a complementary resource that can inform the adjustment of HCWM strategies to specific constraints, such as limited infrastructure or organizational fragmentation, making it easier for healthcare workers to contextualize regulations and apply them in their local settings [37]. The findings support a perspective in which standardized guidelines and local practices are complementary, rather than opposites.

Standardization remains essential for safety and predictability, such as segregation rules, labelling, or routing, but it should be adapted to the capacity of each setting and community and adjust as conditions change across the disaster phases. When standards are applied too rigidly in settings with limited infrastructure, they risk breaking down in practice and contributing to secondary disasters [1,26,46]. This approach supports previous research calling for decentralized and context-specific disaster management systems [52], consistent with findings that disasters vary in scale, geography and intensity, making standardized management responses ineffective [98]. Adaptive capacity, defined here as the ability of a network to reconfigure itself in response to environmental, regulatory, technological and socio-political changes [99,100], must be institutionalised, not improvised. We extend this definition to HCWM, as the capacity for a HCWM system to modify its practices, stakeholder involvement, workflows and use of available technologies in response to changing contextual conditions. An adaptable HCWM system is therefore able to reshape stakeholder salience, incorporate new stakeholders and adjust operational routines to maintain safe waste handling even when standardized HCWM procedures cannot be fully implemented. Indeed, the findings highlighted that the limited institutionalization of community involvement in HCWM planning represents a missed opportunity for inclusive and participatory risk governance. Adaptive regulation, already gaining traction in healthcare innovation [89], could be extended to HCWM to foster context-appropriate solutions.

This hybrid approach directly targets HCWM models that combine the clarity and consistency of standardized HCWM models, with the flexibility of adaptive practices and answers calls for decentralized, context-specific preparedness strategies [52,98].

6. Conclusions

This qualitative study examined HCWM in Kenya and Vietnam through the lens of stakeholder salience [9,14], analyzing how power, urgency and legitimacy evolve across disaster phases. The findings show that positioning HCWM as preparedness aligns directly with Priority 2 (Strengthening disaster risk governance) and Priority 4 (build back better) of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction [43,101] by institutionalising risk-informed practices that reduce the likelihood of cascading effects [56,91]. Conceptually, mapping HCWM responsibilities across disaster phases further adds a temporal and processual dimension to the stakeholder salience model [9,14]. It shows that salience is not static, but rather evolves in response to HCW surges, disruptions, and contextual pressures. This confirms the need for HCWM models that combine the clarity of standardization with the flexibility of adaptive, locally informed practices, so that procedures remain relevant when infrastructure, staffing or oversight are constrained.

Contrary to debris management literature, which emphasizes formal stakeholders and processes [16], our findings show the need to involve local and informal stakeholders early on in planning [102]. Empirically, by extending the stakeholder map beyond formally

mandated stakeholders, the paper demonstrates that HCWM effectiveness increasingly relies on adaptive practices and on the redistribution of salience to local and informal stakeholders, whose influence is rooted in social position rather than material resource control. Building on Fontainha et al. [103] and Schiffling & Piecyk [11], the analysis broadens the humanitarian stakeholder set to include stakewatchers (patients, communities, and informal waste pickers), whose proximity to risk and embedded networks make them critical in contexts of sudden HCW surges. While the literature has begun to recognize the informal sector as a way to relieve an overwhelmed and fragile WM sector [104,105], this study underscores the strategic value of locally embedded stakeholders who are invisible in formal supply chain structures, yet strengthen preparedness by enabling last-mile coordination, diffusion of good practices and low-tech contingencies. The study also underscores the importance of including local voices in data collection and situating HCWM stakeholders within disaster contexts, complementing non-crisis perspectives [90]. Taken together, these insights contribute to ongoing debates on localization and the humanitarian-development-peace (triple nexus) agenda by showing that preparedness in HCWM is most effective when governance recognizes that salience is contingent on disaster phases, integrates stakewatchers, and aligns standards to capacity. Consequently, HCWM should be leveraged as a strategic preparedness tool that reduces secondary health and environmental risks and improves disaster response [23], further contributing to sustainability improvements during disasters [106], and providing valuable resources in steering the supply chain towards circularity.

At the practice level, for HOs, this study offers a new perspective on embedding HCWM across disaster phases, with phase-specific SOPs that anticipate surges and codify collaboration with community stakeholders and informal workers where relevant. The mapping of stakeholders provides guidance on dynamic roles and shows how engaging with local knowledge strengthens supply chain resilience. For policymakers, the study offers new perspective to further align HCWM regulations with local capacity and disaster phases to prevent standards-capacity mismatches while maintaining core safety requirements. Moreover, introducing adaptive regulatory provisions to recognize and protect informal contributors during surge without compromising safety or accountability should be considered. The conclusions of this study can help governments strengthen implementation and align HCWM with broader sustainability objectives and clarifies accountability for mitigation investments, typically neglected by short-term response funding [49]. Finally, healthcare facilities can use the stakeholder mapping to identify which stakeholders become definitive as urgency rises and plan handovers more efficiently across phases. The findings can also allow for a better integration of local knowledge into operational design to increase adherence and local ownership.

Contextually, focusing on Kenya and Vietnam gives a particular perspective, as they are both stable countries, albeit with high inequality, and their disaster settings are similar. Expanding this study to a conflict-zone, or an extremely poor environment would likely yield extremely interesting and useful results. Moreover, additional research is needed to assess how patients, carers, community groups and waste pickers can systematically be included in preparedness, behaviour change and materials recovery, steering HCWM supply chains toward circular practices. Finally, building and validating a model integrating adaptive, locally informed disaster preparedness could advance the agenda of consolidating disaster risk strategies.

Importantly, this paper acknowledges the absence of direct engagement with patients and caregivers as a limitation of this study. The salience of patients and caregivers as stakeholders is largely mediated through the perspectives of formal stakeholders, which raises important questions about representation in HCWM governance. While this study identifies patients and caregivers as among those most directly exposed to the consequences of HCWM failures, their interests are interpreted and transmitted by intermediaries in the data set of this study. This mediation reflects the structural marginalisation of these groups within formal decision-making processes, where their salience is contingent on other stakeholders advocating for their needs. Future research should employ ethically appropriate methods to incorporate these perspectives directly.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Margot Rocheteau: Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Writing – original draft. **Sarah Schiffling:** Funding acquisition, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Virva Tuomala:** Funding acquisition, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Pamela Steele:** Funding acquisition, Validation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Margot Rocheteau reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. Virva Tuomala reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. Margot Rocheteau reports financial support was provided by Hans Bang Foundation. Sarah Schiffling reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. Pamela Steele reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe. Virva Tuomala reports financial support was provided by Business Finland. Sarah Schiffling reports financial support was provided by Business Finland. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The authors declare that this research was supported by funding Horizon Europe, under grant No 101135392, Hans Bang Stiftelsen, and Business Finland under grant 7777/31/2023. We are grateful to the two anonymous reviewers for their insightful comments.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2026.106267>.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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